

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIGITAL COMPETENCE AND TECHNOLOGY ATTITUDES OF INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISORS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between digital competence and technology-related attitudes of instructional supervisors in the DepEd Dumaguete City Division, SY 2025-2026 involving 26 out of 28 target respondents, using a descriptive-correlational design. Findings revealed that most respondents possess substantial supervisory experience; however, a majority had not attended ICT-related training, indicating limited exposure to technology-focused professional development. Despite this, instructional supervisors demonstrated a high level of digital competence overall, with strong abilities in safety, information, and communication, whereas content creation and problem-solving emerged as weaker areas. In terms of attitudes, respondents showed a very high positive attitude toward technology, recognizing its importance in communication, information access, decision-making, and productivity, as well as a very high level of anxiety and dependence on it. They also exhibited a very low negative attitude and a very low preference for task switching, indicating minimal resistance and a focused work approach. Correlation analysis revealed significant relationships between digital competence and position, supervisory experience, and ICT-related training, with ICT training showing the strongest positive connection. Positive attitudes were significantly associated with higher digital competence, while negative attitudes showed an inverse relationship, whereas anxiety/dependence and task switching were not significant predictors.

Keywords: *Digital competence; instructional supervisors; technology attitudes; ICT-related training; educational leadership*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of digital technologies has significantly transformed educational systems worldwide, reshaping instructional supervision, school management, and communication. In the digital era, educational leaders are expected to demonstrate not only technical proficiency but also the capacity to effectively integrate technology in improving instructional practices and organizational efficiency (Cabaron, 2023; Alruthaya et al., 2021). As schools continue to adapt to technology-driven environments, instructional supervisors play a critical role in ensuring that digital tools are effectively used to monitor instruction, support teachers, and enhance school improvement initiatives.

Digital competence has become an essential requirement for educators in the twenty-first century. It refers to the confident, critical, and responsible use of digital technologies for professional and educational purposes, encompassing skills in information processing, communication, content creation, safety, and problem-solving (European Commission, 2022). Studies have shown that educators with higher levels of digital competence are more capable of integrating technology into their professional tasks and adapting to evolving educational demands (Buenaventura, 2026; Abella & Dela Rosa, 2023). This suggests that digital competence is a key determinant of effective educational leadership in technology-rich environments.

Along with digital competence, technology attitudes have been recognized as a significant factor influencing technology adoption and utilization in educational settings. Positive attitudes toward technology enhance the likelihood of effective technology integration, whereas negative perceptions, resistance, or technology-related anxiety may hinder its use (Igpit & Alpuerto, 2022; Subingsubing & Guhao, 2025). This perspective is supported by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which posits that individuals' attitudes toward technology influence their behavioral intention to adopt and use technological systems (Davis, 1989). Recent educational studies have further demonstrated that positive attitudes toward technology are associated with greater acceptance, readiness, and integration of digital tools among educators and educational leaders (Igpit & Alpuerto, 2022; Subingsubing & Guhao, 2025). Thus, digital competence and technology attitudes together provide a comprehensive framework for understanding how educational leaders engage with and utilize digital technologies in their professional practice.

In the Philippine context, the Department of Education (DepEd) has continuously strengthened its efforts to integrate Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in school governance and instructional delivery. Instructional supervisors, including principals, assistant principals, and master teachers are expected to utilize digital platforms for instructional monitoring, data management, professional development, and communication with stakeholders (Salva et al., 2023; Rodriguez, 2022). Their effectiveness in performing these roles is increasingly dependent on both their digital competence and their disposition toward technology use.

However, existing literature reveals that most studies on digital competence and technology attitudes have focused primarily on teachers and general school administrators, with limited attention given to instructional supervisors. Recent research

confirms that while digital competence and attitudes toward technology have been widely examined, there remains a gap in understanding their relationship within specific leadership groups in education (Villamor, 2025; Galaraga & Alpuerto, 2022). Moreover, limited evidence exists regarding how these variables interact in localized educational settings, particularly in Philippine school divisions.

In Schools Division Office (SDO) Dumaguete City, instructional supervisors such as principals, assistant principals, and master teachers play a vital role in ensuring instructional quality and supporting school improvement. As educational processes become increasingly digitized, it is essential to understand their level of digital competence and their attitudes toward technology. However, no known local study has yet comprehensively examined the relationship between these variables in this context. This gap highlights the need for empirical evidence that can inform targeted professional development programs and strengthen technology integration in instructional supervision.

Therefore, this study aimed to determine the relationship between digital competence and technology attitudes of instructional supervisors in the secondary schools of Dumaguete City Division. The findings of this study are expected to provide valuable insights for enhancing ICT-related capacity-building programs and improving instructional leadership practices in a digitally evolving educational environment.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship between digital competence and attitudes of instructional supervisors in the secondary schools of the Dumaguete City Division. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the instructional supervisors in terms of:
 - 1.1 position
 - 1.2 years of supervisory experience; and
 - 1.3 relevant ICT-related training attended for the last 5 years?
2. What is the level of digital competence of instructional supervisors in terms of:
 - 2.1 information;
 - 2.2 communication;
 - 2.3 content creation;
 - 2.4 safety; and
 - 2.5 problem-solving?
3. What is the level of attitudes of instructional supervisors toward the use of digital technologies in instructional supervision?
4. Is there a significant relationship between respondents' profile in terms of position, instructional supervisory experience, and ICT-related training, and the digital competence of instructional supervisors?
5. Is there a significant relationship between respondents' profile in terms of position, instructional supervisory experience, and ICT-related training, and the attitudes of instructional supervisors toward digital technologies?
6. Is there a significant relationship between digital competence and attitudes of instructional supervisors?

Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile in terms of position, instructional supervisory experience, and ICT-related training, and the digital competence of instructional supervisors.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile in terms of position, instructional supervisory experience, and ICT-related training, and the attitudes of instructional supervisors toward digital technologies.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between the digital competence and the attitudes of instructional supervisors toward digital technologies.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. The descriptive component was utilized to determine the profile, level of digital competence, and attitudes toward digital technology of instructional supervisors in the secondary schools of the Dumaguete City Division. Specifically, it described the respondents' position, years of instructional supervising experience, and number of ICT-related trainings attended, as well as their levels of digital competence and attitudes toward digital technology.

The correlational component was used to examine the relationships between the respondents' profile variables and their digital competence and attitudes toward digital technology. This design was deemed appropriate because it enabled the researcher to investigate the extent to which the variables are associated without manipulating any of them. Through this approach, the study sought to provide a comprehensive understanding of the digital competence and attitudes of instructional supervisors and the factors that may influence them.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were the instructional supervisors in the secondary schools of the Dumaguete City Division, specifically the principals, assistant principals, and master teachers. These educational leaders play significant roles in instructional supervision, curriculum implementation, teacher mentoring, and the promotion of quality teaching and learning within their respective schools.

The respondents were selected because of their supervisory responsibilities and involvement in instructional leadership, which require the use of digital technologies in carrying out administrative and instructional functions. As key instructional leaders, their digital competence and attitudes toward digital technology are essential in supporting technology integration and digital transformation initiatives in schools.

Population and Sampling

The population of this study consisted of all instructional supervisors in the secondary schools of the Dumaguete City Division, comprising 28 respondents, including principals, assistant principals, and master teachers. Since the population was relatively small and manageable, the study employed total population sampling, wherein all members of the population were invited to participate in the study.

Of the 28 instructional supervisors (principals, assistant principals and master teachers) identified, 26 voluntarily participated and completed the survey questionnaire, yielding a response rate of 92.86%. The data gathered from these respondents served as the basis for the analysis and interpretation of the study's findings.

Research Instruments

The primary instrument used in this study was a structured survey questionnaire composed of three parts.

Part I gathered the respondents' profile information, including their position, years of instructional supervising experience, and the number of ICT-related trainings attended for the last five years.

Part II assessed the respondents' level of digital competence using the vINCI Digital Skills Questionnaire (DSQ), which was adopted from the Active and Assisted Living (AAL) Programmer's vINCI Project (Active and Assisted Living Programme, 2017). The instrument measures respondents' digital skills and competencies across various aspects of technology use. Responses were rated using a five-point Likert scale, with higher scores indicating higher levels of digital competence.

Part III measured the respondents' attitudes toward digital technology using a five-point Likert scale adopted from Rosen et al. (2013) study. This section evaluated the respondents' perceptions, feelings, and dispositions toward the use of digital technologies in carrying out their instructional and administrative responsibilities.

The instruments were selected because they are appropriate for assessing the variables under investigation and aligned with the objectives of the study. The adopted instruments were subjected to reliability testing to ensure the consistency of the data gathered and were based on previously validated measures to support content validity.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the conduct of the study, permission to administer the survey was secured from the schools-division superintendent. Upon approval, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaire to the identified respondents through an online platform to facilitate convenient and efficient data collection.

The respondents were informed of the purpose of the study and were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire. Participation in the survey was voluntary, and confidentiality of the information provided was assured. After all responses were collected, the data were organized, tallied, and subjected to appropriate statistical treatment for analysis and interpretation in accordance with the objectives of the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered in this study were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to address the research objectives.

Frequency counts and percentages were used to describe the respondents' profile in terms of position, years of instructional supervising experience, and number of ICT-related trainings attended. *Mean* was utilized to determine the level of digital competence and attitudes toward digital technology among the respondents.

To determine the significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their digital competence and attitudes toward digital technology, as well as the relationship between digital competence and attitudes toward digital technology, the *Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r)* was employed. All statistical analyses were conducted using an appropriate level of significance to test the study's hypotheses.

RESULTS

The results of the study are presented in both tabular and textual form to provide a clear account of the data. These are accompanied by analysis and interpretation to comprehensively address the research objectives.

Demographic Profile

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of position, years of instructional supervisory experience, and number of ICT-related trainings attended during the last five years.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents (position, instructional supervisory experience, and number of ICT related trainings)

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Position		
Principal	8	30.77%
Assistant Principal	11	42.31%
Master Teacher	7	26.92%
Total	26	100.00%
Years of Instructional Supervisory Experience		
1–5 years	6	23.08%
6 – 10 years	10	38.46%
11 – 15 years	2	7.69%
16 – 20 years and above	8	30.77%
Total	26	100.00%
No. of ICT Related Trainings the last 5 years		

0 or None	14	53.85%
1 – 2 times	10	38.46%
3 – 5 times	2	7.69%
Total	26	100.00%

For position, the largest group of respondents were Assistant Principals, comprising 42.31% (11) of the total respondents. This was followed by Principals with 30.77% (8), while Master Teachers accounted for 26.92% (7). The distribution indicates that instructional supervision in the schools is performed by personnel occupying different leadership roles, with Assistant Principals constituting the largest proportion of instructional supervisors.

Regarding years of instructional supervisory experience, the highest percentage of respondents (38.46% or 10) had been performing supervisory functions for 6–10 years. This was followed by those with 16–20 years and above of experience, representing 30.77% (8) of the respondents. Meanwhile, 23.08% (6) had 1–5 years of supervisory experience, while only 7.69% (2) reported having 11–15 years of experience. These findings suggest that most instructional supervisors have accumulated several years of supervisory practice, providing them with substantial exposure to instructional leadership and teacher support activities.

With respect to ICT-related trainings attended during the last five years, more than half of the respondents (53.85% or 14) reported that they had not attended any ICT-related training. Ten respondents (38.46%) attended one to two trainings, while only two respondents (7.69%) participated in three to five ICT-related trainings. This indicates that opportunities for ICT-related professional development among instructional supervisors have been relatively limited.

Digital Competence

Table 2. Digital Competence

Digital Skills	Mean	Interpretation
Information		
I can look for information online using a search engine.	4.92	Very High
I know not all online information is reliable.	4.92	Very High
I can save or store files or content (e.g., text, pictures, music, videos, web pages) and retrieve them once saved or stored	4.00	Very High
Total	4.62	Very High
Communication		
I can communicate with others using a mobile phone, Voice over IP (e.g., Skype), e-mail, or chat – using basic features (e.g., voice messaging, SMS, sending and receiving e-mails, text exchange)	4.96	Very High
I can share files and content using simple tools	4.46	Very High

I know I can use digital technologies to interact with services (as governments, banks, and hospitals).	3.96	High
I am aware of social networking sites and online collaboration tools.	4.96	Very High
I am aware that when using digital tools, certain communication rules apply (e.g., when commenting, sharing personal information)	3.69	High
Total	4.41	Very High
Content Creation		
I can produce simple digital content (e.g., text, tables, images, audio files) in at least one format using digital tools.	2.50	Low
I can make basic edits to content produced by others.	1.85	Low
I know that content can be covered by copyright.	3.31	Moderate
I can apply and modify simple functions and settings of software and applications that I use (e.g., change default settings).	1.88	Low
Total	2.38	Low
Safety		
I can take basic steps to protect my devices (e.g., using antivirus software and passwords)	4.58	Very High
I am aware that my credentials (username and password) can be stolen	4.65	Very High
I know I should not reveal private information online	4.88	Very High
I know that using digital technology too extensively can affect my health.	4.73	Very High
Total	4.71	Very High
Problem Solving		
I can find support and assistance when a technical problem occurs or when using a new device, program or application.	3.12	Moderate
I know how to solve some routine problems (e.g. close program, re-start computer, re-install/update program, check internet connection).	2.38	Low
I know that digital tools can help me in solving problems. I am also aware that they have their limitations.	4.19	High
When confronted with a technological or non-technological problem, I can use the digital tools I know to solve it.	2.96	Moderate
Total	3.16	Moderate
Grand Mean	3.86	High

Range: 1.00 – 1.80 Very Low; 1.81 – 2.60 Low; 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate; 3.41 – 4.20 High; 4.21 – 5.00 Very High

Table 2 presents the level of digital competence of instructional supervisors across the five dimensions of digital competence: information, communication, content creation, safety, and problem solving. The results revealed a grand mean of 3.86, interpreted as High Digital Competence. This indicates that the respondents generally possess the knowledge and skills necessary to use digital technologies in carrying out their

supervisory and leadership responsibilities. However, the results also show notable differences across the various dimensions of digital competence.

Among the five dimensions, Safety obtained the highest mean score of 4.71, interpreted as Very High Competence. The respondents demonstrated strong awareness of protecting devices through passwords and security measures, safeguarding personal information, and understanding the possible effects of excessive technology use. The highest-rated indicator was awareness that private information should not be disclosed online ($M = 4.88$). This finding suggests that instructional supervisors are highly conscious of cybersecurity and responsible digital behavior. According to the Digital Competence Framework (DigComp 2.2), digital safety includes protecting devices, personal data, privacy, health, and well-being while using digital technologies (European Commission, 2022). Such competence is essential among educational leaders who regularly manage sensitive school and learner information (European Commission, 2022).

The second highest dimension was Information, with a mean of 4.62, interpreted as Very High Competence. Respondents reported strong abilities in searching for information online, recognizing that not all online information is reliable, and storing and retrieving digital files when needed. These findings indicate that instructional supervisors can access and manage digital information effectively. According to DigComp 2.2, information and data literacy involves identifying information needs, locating and evaluating digital information, and organizing digital content efficiently (European Commission, 2022). These competencies are important for instructional supervisors who regularly gather, analyze, and utilize educational data in decision-making and instructional monitoring.

Similarly, the Communication dimension obtained a mean of 4.41, interpreted as Very High Competence. Respondents demonstrated competence in communicating through emails, messaging applications, and online collaboration platforms. The highest-rated indicators were the ability to communicate using digital technologies and awareness of social networking and collaboration tools ($M = 4.96$). This suggests that instructional supervisors are comfortable using digital communication tools to coordinate with teachers, school heads, and other stakeholders. The DigComp 2.2 framework identifies communication and collaboration as a key area of digital competence, emphasizing effective interaction, information sharing, and participation through digital technologies (European Commission, 2022). The widespread use of digital communication platforms in schools may have contributed to the respondents' high competence in this area.

In contrast, Problem Solving obtained a mean of 3.16, interpreted as Moderate Competence. While respondents agreed that digital tools can help solve problems ($M = 4.19$), they reported lower competence in troubleshooting routine technical issues such as resolving connectivity problems or restarting malfunctioning applications ($M = 2.38$). This finding suggests that instructional supervisors may understand the benefits of technology but may not always possess the technical expertise needed to independently address technology-related challenges. According to DigComp 2.2, problem-solving involves identifying digital needs, resolving technical issues, adapting technologies to specific situations, and continuously updating digital skills (European Commission, 2022). As educational institutions increasingly rely on digital technologies, the ability to solve technical problems becomes a critical component of effective instructional leadership.

The lowest-rated dimension was Content Creation, with a mean of 2.38, interpreted as Low Competence. Respondents reported limited ability to create digital materials, edit content, modify software settings, and apply copyright principles. The lowest-rated indicator was the ability to make basic edits to content created by others (M = 1.85). This finding indicates that while instructional supervisors are confident users of technology for communication and information management, they may have less experience in producing and managing digital content. According to DigComp 2.2, digital content creation involves creating, editing, and improving digital resources while observing copyright and licensing requirements (European Commission, 2022). The low rating in this dimension suggests a need for further professional development focused on creating instructional resources and digital learning materials.

Technology Attitude

Table 3.1 Positive attitudes

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
I feel it is important to be able to find any information whenever I want online.	4.69	Very High
I feel it is important to be able to access the Internet any time I want.	4.77	Very High
I think it is important to keep up with the latest trends in technology.	4.65	Very High
Technology will provide solutions to many of our problems.	4.38	Very High
With technology anything is possible.	4.19	High
I feel that I get more accomplished because of technology.	4.04	High
Total	4.46	Very High

Legend: 1.00-1.80 Very Low; 1.81-2.60 Low; 2.61-3.40 Moderate; 3.41-4.20 High; 4.21-5.00 Very High

Table 3.1 presents the respondents' positive attitudes toward technology. The overall mean of 4.46 indicates a Very High Positive Attitude toward technology. This suggests that instructional supervisors generally view technology as valuable, beneficial, and important in their professional and personal lives.

Among the indicators, the highest-rated statement was "I feel it is important to be able to access the Internet any time I want" (M = 4.77), followed by "I feel it is important to be able to find any information whenever I want online" (M = 4.69), and "I think it is important to keep up with the latest trends in technology" (M = 4.65), all interpreted as Very High Positive Attitude. These findings indicate that respondents highly value immediate access to information, connectivity, and technological advancements. Such results reflect the growing importance of digital technologies in educational leadership, communication, and decision-making processes.

The indicators "Technology will provide solutions to many of our problems" (M = 4.38) and "With technology anything is possible" (M = 4.19) also received favorable ratings, suggesting that respondents recognize technology as a useful tool for improving efficiency and addressing workplace challenges. Likewise, respondents agreed that they become more accomplished because of technology (M = 4.04), indicating an appreciation of technology's contribution to productivity and professional effectiveness.

Table 3.2 Anxiety/Dependence

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
I get anxious when I don't have my cell phone.	4.50	Very High
I get anxious when I don't have the Internet available to me.	4.58	Very High
I am dependent on my technology.	4.54	Very High
Total	4.54	Very High

Legend: 1.00-1.80 Very Low; 1.81-2.60 Low; 2.61-3.40 Moderate; 3.41-4.20 High; 4.21-5.00 Very High

Table 3.2 presents the respondents' level of anxiety and dependence on technology. The overall mean of 4.54 indicates a Very High Anxiety/Dependence toward technology. This finding suggests that respondents have become highly reliant on technological devices and internet connectivity in their daily activities and professional responsibilities.

The highest-rated statement was "I get anxious when I don't have the Internet available to me" (M = 4.58), followed by "I am dependent on my technology" (M = 4.54) and "I get anxious when I don't have my cell phone" (M = 4.50), all interpreted as Very High Anxiety/Dependence. These findings indicate that technology has become an integral part of respondents' personal and professional lives.

Table 3.3 Negative attitudes

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
New technology makes people waste too much time.	1.73	Very Low
New technology makes life more complicated.	1.46	Very Low
New technology makes people more isolated.	1.58	Very Low
Total	1.59	Very Low

Legend: 1.00-1.80 Very Low; 1.81-2.60 Low; 2.61-3.40 Moderate; 3.41-4.20 High; 4.21-5.00 Very High

Table 3.3 presents the respondents' negative attitudes toward technology. The overall mean of 1.59, interpreted as Very Low Negative Attitude, indicates that instructional supervisors generally do not hold unfavorable views regarding technology.

Among the indicators, "New technology makes people waste too much time" obtained the highest mean of 1.73, while "New technology makes people more isolated" (M = 1.58) and "New technology makes life more complicated" (M = 1.46) also received ratings within

the Very Low Negative Attitude range. These findings suggest that respondents largely disagree with common negative perceptions of technology.

Table 3.4 Preference for task switching

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
I prefer to work on several projects in a day, rather than completing one project and then switching to another.	1.38	Very Low
When doing many assignments, I like to switch back and forth between them rather than do one at a time.	1.42	Very Low
*I like to finish one task before focusing on anything else.	1.38	Very Low
When I have a task to complete, I like to break it up by switching to other tasks intermittently.	1.31	Very Low
Total	1.38	Very Low

*Scoring is reversed with strongly agree = 1 and strongly disagree = 5.

Legend: 1.00-1.80 Very Low; 1.81-2.60 Low; 2.61-3.40 Moderate; 3.41-4.20 High; 4.21-5.00 Very High

Table 3.4 presents the respondents' preference for task switching. The overall mean of 1.38, interpreted as Very Low Preference for Task Switching, indicates that instructional supervisors generally prefer focusing on one task at a time rather than frequently switching between multiple tasks.

All indicators were rated within the Very Low Preference for Task Switching category. The highest-rated statement was "When doing some assignments, I like to switch back and forth between them rather than do one at a time" (M = 1.42), while the lowest-rated statement was "When I have a task to complete, I like to break it up by switching to other tasks intermittently" (M = 1.31).

It is important to note that the scoring for this dimension was reversed, meaning that lower scores indicate a stronger preference for completing one task before moving to another. Thus, the findings suggest that respondents generally favor a focused and organized approach to work rather than multitasking.

Table 4. Relationship between respondents' profile and digital competence

Digital Competence (n=30)	Correlation Coefficient (r)	r²	p-value
Position	-0.4163	0.1733	0.034*
Instructional supervisory experience	-0.3886	0.1510	0.050*
ICT Related training	0.4910	0.2411	0.011*

*Significance at p = <0.05

Table 4 presents the relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their level of digital competence. Specifically, the table shows the correlation coefficients, coefficients of determination (r²), and corresponding p-values for position, instructional

supervisory experience, and ICT-related training. The results reveal that all three profile variables have statistically significant relationships with digital competence since their p-values are equal to or less than the 0.05 level of significance.

The respondents' position was found to have a significant negative relationship with digital competence ($r = -0.4163$, $p = 0.034$). The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.1733$) indicates that approximately 17.33% of the variation in digital competence may be associated with differences in position. The negative correlation suggests that as respondents move across higher positions, digital competence tends to decrease. This finding may indicate differences in technology-related responsibilities, exposure, or opportunities among Principals, Assistant Principals, and Master Teachers. Those in lower positions in leadership such as Master Teacher may demonstrate higher digital competence than others due to more frequent engagement with digital tools and technologies during classroom observations and other related tasks.

Similarly, instructional supervisory experience exhibited a significant negative relationship with digital competence ($r = -0.3886$, $p = 0.050$). The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.1510$) indicates that approximately 15.10% of the variance in digital competence can be attributed to differences in supervisory experience. The negative correlation indicates that respondents with longer supervisory experience tend to report lower levels of digital competence compared to those with fewer years of service. This may be explained by the delegation of technology-related tasks to lower-ranked instructional supervisors, as school principals are often preoccupied with broader responsibilities such as managing school operations, fostering external partnerships, and addressing diverse administrative demands.

In contrast, ICT-related training demonstrated a significant positive relationship with digital competence ($r = 0.4910$, $p = 0.011$). Among the three profile variables, ICT-related training showed the strongest relationship with digital competence. The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.2411$) indicates that approximately 24.11% of the variance in digital competence may be explained by participation in ICT-related training programs. The positive correlation suggests that respondents who attended more ICT-related trainings tended to have higher levels of digital competence.

Table 5. Relationship between respondents' profiles and attitudes

Profile (n=26)		Correlation Coefficient (r)	r ²	p-value
Position	Positive attitudes	-0.4900	0.2401	0.011*
	Anxiety/Dependence	-0.5006	0.2506	0.0092*
	Negative attitudes	0.3344	0.1118	0.095
	Preference for task switching	0.3955	0.1564	0.045*
Instructional supervisory experience	Positive attitudes	-0.2428	0.0590	0.232
	Anxiety/Dependence	-0.4140	0.1714	0.035*
	Negative attitudes	0.3172	0.1006	0.114

	Preference for task switching	0.0680	0.0046	0.741)
ICT Related training	Positive attitudes	0.5216	0.2721	0.0063*
	Anxiety/Dependence	0.2058	0.0423	0.313
	Negative attitudes	-0.2647	0.0701	0.191
	Preference for task switching	-0.2879	0.0829	0.154

*Significance at $p = <0.05$

Table 5 examines the relationship between respondents' professional profile variables—position, instructional supervisory experience, and ICT-related training, and their attitudes toward technology. The results reveal several significant correlations, highlighting how these professional characteristics influence supervisors' perspectives and behaviors in digital contexts.

For position, the data show significant negative correlations with both positive attitudes ($r = -0.4900$, $p = 0.011$) and anxiety/dependence ($r = -0.5006$, $p = 0.0092$). This suggests that higher-ranking supervisors tend to exhibit fewer positive attitudes toward technology and lower levels of anxiety or dependence. Interestingly, position also shows a significant positive correlation with preference for task switching ($r = 0.3955$, $p = 0.045$), indicating that those in higher positions may be more inclined to multitask or shift between tasks when using technology. The r^2 values (24–25%) suggest that position explains a substantial portion of the variance in these attitudes.

For instructional supervisory experience, only anxiety/dependence showed a significant negative correlation ($r = -0.4140$, $p = 0.035$). This implies that supervisors with longer experience tend to feel less anxious or dependent on technology, possibly due to greater confidence in managing instructional responsibilities. However, no significant relationships were found between experience and positive attitudes, negative attitudes, or task-switching preferences, suggesting that years of service alone do not strongly shape overall attitudes toward technology.

For ICT-related training, the strongest and most positive correlation emerged with positive attitudes ($r = 0.5216$, $p = 0.0063$). Supervisors who received ICT training were more likely to demonstrate favorable attitudes toward technology use, with training explaining 27% of the variance in positive attitudes. Although correlations with other attitude dimensions were not statistically significant, the direction of the coefficients suggests that training may reduce negative attitudes and discourage unnecessary task switching, even if these effects were not strong enough to reach significance.

Table 6. Relationship between digital competence and attitudes

Digital Competence (n=26)	Correlation Coefficient (r)	r^2	p-value
Positive attitudes	0.5255	0.2761	0.0058*
Anxiety/Dependence	0.3541	0.1254	0.076

Negative attitudes	-0.4729	0.2236	0.015*
Preference for task switching	-0.3738	0.1397	0.060

*Significance at $p = <0.05$

Table 6 shows the correlation between digital competence and various technology-related attitudes among instructional supervisors. Positive attitudes toward technology were significantly correlated with digital competence ($r = 0.5255$, $p = 0.0058$), explaining 27.61% of the variance. Negative attitudes were significantly and inversely correlated ($r = -0.4729$, $p = 0.015$), accounting for 22.36% of the variance. Anxiety/dependence ($r = 0.3541$, $p = 0.076$) and preference for task switching ($r = -0.3738$, $p = 0.060$) showed moderate correlations but were not statistically significant.

The results indicate that supervisors with stronger digital competence tend to hold more positive attitudes toward technology, while those with weaker competence are more likely to harbor negative attitudes. The non-significant correlations with anxiety/dependence and task switching suggest that these attitudes may not directly predict competence, though they could influence technology use indirectly.

DISCUSSION

The study examined the relationship between digital competence and technology-related attitudes of instructional supervisors in the DepEd Dumaguete City Division, with 26 respondents participating in a descriptive-correlational design. Significant findings revealed as follows:

Respondents' Profile

The profile of the instructional supervisors reveals that instructional leadership responsibilities are distributed among various educational leaders, including principals, assistant principals, and master teachers. In terms of position, assistant principals comprised the largest group of respondents (42.31%), followed by principals (30.77%) and master teachers (26.92%). The findings suggest that instructional supervision is not solely the responsibility of school principals but is shared among different school leaders who collectively contribute to monitoring instruction, supporting teachers, and improving educational outcomes. The relatively high proportion of assistant principals may be attributed to the organizational structure of some schools in the division, where two or more assistant principals are assigned to support school management and instructional supervision. As a result, assistant principals outnumbered principals in the respondent pool. Their substantial representation further highlights their active involvement in day-to-day instructional supervision, teacher mentoring, curriculum implementation, and school improvement initiatives. This reflects the distributed leadership approach increasingly practiced in schools, wherein leadership responsibilities are shared among multiple educational leaders to enhance instructional effectiveness and organizational performance.

On the other hand, the findings on instructional supervisory experience indicate that most respondents possess substantial experience in carrying out leadership and supervisory

responsibilities. The largest proportion of instructional supervisors (38.46%) reported having six to ten years of supervisory experience, followed by 30.77% who had sixteen years or more of experience. Meanwhile, 23.08% had one to five years of experience, and only 7.69% had eleven to fifteen years of experience. These results suggest that most instructional supervisors have accumulated significant professional experience that enables them to develop competencies in instructional leadership, curriculum implementation, teacher mentoring, classroom observation, and performance monitoring. Extensive supervisory experience is important in enhancing leadership effectiveness, as it allows educational leaders to gain a deeper understanding of instructional practices, teacher development needs, and school improvement initiatives. Research has shown that experienced school leaders are more likely to exhibit strong instructional leadership behaviors and are better prepared to support teachers in implementing educational reforms and innovations (Hallinger & Walker, 2021; Liu & Hallinger, 2022). Consequently, the considerable supervisory experience of the respondents may contribute positively to their ability to make informed decisions, provide constructive feedback, and effectively address challenges within the educational environment.

Moreover, the findings on ICT related trainings revealed that more than half of the respondents (53.85% or 14) had not attended any ICT-related training, indicating limited participation in professional development activities focused on technology. This result may have important implications for the development of digital competence among instructional supervisors, particularly as schools increasingly rely on digital platforms, learning management systems, online communication tools, and data-driven decision-making processes. As educational leaders and mentors, instructional supervisors are expected to possess the knowledge and skills necessary to guide teachers in the effective integration of technology into teaching and learning. Research highlights that professional development is a key factor in enhancing digital competence, as continuous participation in ICT-related training improves technological knowledge, operational skills, confidence, and readiness to utilize digital tools in professional practice (Falloon, 2021; Redecker, 2022). The findings may also be viewed through the lens of the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp 2.2), which emphasizes lifelong learning and continuous professional development as essential for maintaining and advancing digital competence in response to rapidly evolving technologies (Vuorikari, et al., 2022). Likewise, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) suggests that individuals are more likely to adopt and use technology when they perceive it as useful and easy to use, perceptions that are strengthened through training and experience (Al-Rahmi et al., 2022). Therefore, the limited exposure of many instructional supervisors to ICT-related training may hinder their ability to keep pace with emerging technologies and effectively lead digital transformation initiatives within their schools, while those who participate in such training are likely to be better.

Digital Competence

The findings on digital competence revealed that instructional supervisors possess a high level of digital competence, indicating that they generally have the knowledge, skills, and confidence necessary to utilize digital technologies in carrying out their supervisory, managerial, and instructional leadership responsibilities. This suggests that they are

capable of integrating digital tools into various professional tasks, including communication, information management, monitoring, and decision-making. The results are consistent with the Digital Competence Framework (DigComp 2.2), which emphasizes that digitally competent individuals can effectively access and manage information, communicate and collaborate, create digital content, solve problems, and practice responsible and safe use of technology (European Commission, 2022). The overall level of competence observed among the respondents reflects the growing role of digital technologies in educational leadership and administration, particularly in an era characterized by rapid technological advancement and digital transformation.

A closer examination of the dimensions indicates that instructional supervisors demonstrated their strongest competencies in Safety, Information, and Communication. The very high competence in Safety reflects strong awareness of cybersecurity, privacy protection, responsible technology use, and the safeguarding of sensitive information. Such competence is particularly important for instructional supervisors who regularly handle confidential school, teacher, and learner data. Likewise, the very high competence in Information suggests that respondents are proficient in locating, evaluating, organizing, and managing digital information, skills that are essential for evidence-based decision-making and effective instructional supervision. Similarly, the high level of competence in Communication demonstrates that instructional supervisors are comfortable using digital technologies to collaborate, share information, and maintain professional interactions with teachers, school leaders, and other stakeholders. These findings indicate that the respondents have successfully adapted to the communication and information demands of contemporary educational environments.

Despite the generally favorable results, relatively lower levels of competence were observed in Problem Solving and Content Creation. The moderate competence in Problem Solving suggests that while instructional supervisors recognize the value of technology in addressing work-related challenges, they may experience difficulties in troubleshooting technical issues and adapting digital tools to specific contexts. More notably, the lower competence in Content Creation indicates limited skills in developing, editing, modifying, and managing digital resources. This finding implies that instructional supervisors are more confident in using technology for communication and information management than in creating digital content. Such limitations may affect their ability to design innovative digital materials, support technology-enhanced learning initiatives, and provide guidance to teachers in the development of digital instructional resources.

The variation across the dimensions highlights that digital competence is a multidimensional construct that extends beyond the basic use of technology. Effective digital leadership requires not only the ability to access information and communicate through digital platforms but also the capacity to create digital content, solve technical challenges, and adapt to emerging technologies. The relatively lower competence in Content Creation and Problem Solving may be associated with limited participation in ICT-related professional development activities. Recent studies have emphasized that continuous professional development plays a crucial role in enhancing educators' and educational leaders' digital competence, particularly in advanced digital skills such as content development and technology problem solving (Antonietti et al., 2022; Guillén-

Gómez et al., 2022). Therefore, while instructional supervisors demonstrate a generally high level of digital competence, targeted training programs focusing on digital content creation and technical problem-solving skills may further strengthen their ability to lead technology integration and support digital transformation efforts within schools.

Technology Attitude

The findings on attitude toward technology revealed that instructional supervisors possess a very high positive attitude toward technology, indicating that they generally view technology as valuable, beneficial, and essential in both their professional and personal lives. Respondents highly valued access to the internet, the availability of online information, and staying updated with technological developments, reflecting their recognition of technology's role in enhancing communication, decision-making, and work efficiency. They also perceived technology as a useful tool for solving problems and improving productivity. These findings suggest that instructional supervisors are receptive to technological innovations and recognize the potential of digital tools in supporting educational leadership and supervisory functions. Consistent with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), positive perceptions of technology enhance individuals' willingness to adopt and utilize digital systems in their work (Scherer et al., 2021). Similarly, educational leaders with favorable attitudes toward technology are more likely to support innovation and technology integration within schools (Cabero-Almenara et al., 2022).

The results further showed a very high level of anxiety and dependence on technology, indicating that digital devices and internet connectivity have become deeply embedded in the respondents' daily activities and professional responsibilities. Many instructional supervisors reported feelings of discomfort when access to technology or the internet was unavailable, suggesting a strong reliance on digital tools for communication, information access, and administrative tasks. While such dependence may reflect the successful integration of technology into professional practice, it also highlights the need to promote digital well-being and balanced technology use. Previous studies have noted that excessive reliance on technology may contribute to anxiety and psychological discomfort when access is disrupted (Elhai et al., 2021; Servidio et al., 2021).

In contrast, respondents demonstrated a very low negative attitude toward technology, indicating minimal resistance to technological change and a generally favorable perception of digital tools. They largely disagreed with the notion that technology wastes time, increases social isolation, or complicates daily life. This finding suggests that instructional supervisors perceive technology as an asset rather than a burden, which may facilitate its adoption and effective integration into educational settings. Research has shown that individuals with lower negative attitudes toward technology are more likely to embrace digital innovations and support technology-enhanced practices in their organizations (Falloon, 2022).

Likewise, the respondents exhibited a very low preference for task switching, suggesting a tendency to focus on one task at a time rather than engage in multitasking. Since lower scores in this dimension indicate a

greater preference for task completion before moving to another activity, the findings imply that instructional supervisors favor a systematic and organized approach to work. Such a tendency may be advantageous in instructional supervision, where careful analysis, evaluation, and decision-making are required. Research suggests that sustained attention to a single task often promotes greater concentration, accuracy, and productivity, whereas excessive multitasking may reduce efficiency and increase cognitive demands (Mark et al., 2022).

Taken together, the findings indicate that instructional supervisors hold highly favorable attitudes toward technology, demonstrate strong reliance on digital tools, exhibit minimal resistance to technological change, and prefer focused task completion. These characteristics create a supportive foundation for technology integration and digital leadership in schools, as positive attitudes toward technology are often associated with greater acceptance, utilization, and promotion of digital innovations in educational settings.

Relationship between Profile and Digital Competence

The test of relationship between profile and digital competence reveals significant relationship between position and digital competence. It suggests that digital skills may vary according to the responsibilities and technology demands associated with different leadership roles. Instructional supervisors occupying positions that require frequent use of digital tools for communication, data management, instructional monitoring, and decision-making may have greater opportunities to develop and strengthen their digital competence. This finding supports previous studies indicating that professional roles and workplace expectations influence the extent to which educational leaders acquire and utilize digital competencies in their daily functions (Falloon, 2021; Sánchez-Caballé et al., 2022).

Similarly, the significant relationship between instructional supervisory experience and digital competence indicates that years of experience alone do not necessarily translate into stronger digital skills. The negative relationship observed may suggest that supervisors who entered leadership positions more recently have been exposed to technology-rich environments during their professional preparation and career development, making them more familiar with contemporary digital tools and practices. Conversely, more experienced supervisors may have developed their professional expertise during periods when technology played a less prominent role in educational administration. While extensive experience contributes substantially to leadership effectiveness, adapting to rapidly evolving digital technologies often requires continuous learning and skill enhancement. Similar patterns have been reported in recent studies showing that educators with fewer years of service sometimes demonstrate higher levels of digital competence due to greater exposure to digital learning environments and emerging technologies (Lucas et al., 2021; Guillén-Gámez et al., 2022).

Among all profile variables, ICT-related training exhibited the strongest relationship with digital competence, underscoring the critical role of professional development in enhancing digital skills among instructional supervisors. Participation in ICT-related training provides opportunities to acquire technological knowledge, develop practical

digital skills, build confidence, and improve the effective use of digital tools in professional practice. This finding is consistent with the Digital Competence Framework (DigComp 2.2), which emphasizes lifelong learning and continuous professional development as essential components of digital competence development (European Commission, 2022). Recent studies likewise affirm that ICT-related training significantly improves educators' digital competence, technology integration practices, and readiness to lead digital transformation initiatives within educational institutions (Guillén-Gámez et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2023). The findings therefore highlight the importance of sustained professional development programs in strengthening the digital competence of instructional supervisors and preparing them to effectively lead technology-enhanced educational environments.

Relationship between Profile and Attitudes

The test of relationship between profile and attitudes reveals position is significantly associated with positive attitudes, anxiety/dependence, and preference for task switching. The negative relationship between position and positive attitudes suggests that respondents occupying higher supervisory positions may exhibit less enthusiasm toward technology compared with those in lower positions. One possible explanation is that higher-ranking personnel often face greater administrative responsibilities and accountability demands, which may lead them to view technology more as a work requirement than as a beneficial innovation. This finding supports the view of Rosen et al. (2013) that attitudes toward technology vary according to users' professional responsibilities and patterns of technology engagement.

Interestingly, position also shows a significant negative relationship with anxiety/dependence. This suggests that higher-ranking supervisors tend to experience lower levels of anxiety related to technology use and are less dependent on technological devices. Individuals in leadership roles may possess greater confidence in decision-making and problem-solving, allowing them to adapt more effectively to technological challenges. This finding is consistent with studies emphasizing that leadership experience and professional maturity contribute to higher levels of self-efficacy in technology use (Liu & Hallinger, 2022).

The significant positive relationship between position and preference for task switching may indicate that supervisors in higher positions are required to manage multiple responsibilities simultaneously, frequently alternating between communication platforms, digital reports, monitoring systems, and administrative tasks. As educational leadership increasingly relies on digital technologies, multitasking has become a common requirement among educational supervisors. According to Servidio et al. (2021), individuals who frequently engage with multiple digital tools often develop greater tendencies toward technology-mediated multitasking behaviors.

Regarding instructional supervisory experience, the significant negative relationship with anxiety/dependence suggests that more experienced supervisors are generally more comfortable using technology and less likely to feel anxious when engaging with digital tools. Experience may contribute to confidence and adaptability, enabling supervisors to navigate technological demands more effectively. This finding aligns with the work of

Falloon (2021), who emphasized that competence and confidence in digital environments often develop through continuous exposure and practical application over time.

The absence of significant relationships between supervisory experience and positive attitudes, negative attitudes, and preference for task switching suggests that years of experience alone may not be sufficient to shape broader technology attitudes. Instead, attitudes may be influenced more strongly by opportunities for professional development, organizational culture, and personal motivation.

Among all profile variables, ICT-related training emerged as the strongest factor associated with positive attitudes toward technology. The significant positive correlation indicates that respondents who participate in more ICT-related training tend to develop more favorable perceptions of technology. Training programs likely enhance technological knowledge, improve confidence, and provide opportunities for successful technology experiences, thereby fostering positive attitudes. This finding supports the Technology Acceptance Model, which posits that individuals are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward technology when they perceive it as useful and easy to use. Similarly, Al-Rahmi et al. (2022) reported that technology-related learning opportunities significantly improve users' acceptance and positive perceptions of digital technologies.

The lack of significant relationships between ICT-related training and anxiety/dependence, negative attitudes, and preference for task switching may indicate that while training strengthens positive perceptions, other psychological and contextual factors influence these dimensions. Factors such as personality, workload, organizational expectations, and individual technology habits may play a greater role in shaping anxiety levels and multitasking behaviors.

Relationship between Digital Competence and Technology Attitudes

The analysis revealed significant relationships between digital competence and technology-related attitudes among instructional supervisors. Positive attitudes toward technology showed a significant positive correlation with digital competence, explaining a meaningful portion of variance. On the contrary, negative attitudes demonstrated a significant inverse relationship, indicating that higher levels of negative perception are associated with lower digital competence. However, anxiety/dependence and preference for task switching both showed moderate but non-significant relationships with digital competence.

The results indicate that supervisors with stronger digital competence tend to hold more positive attitudes toward technology, while those with weaker competence are more likely to hold negative attitudes. The non-significant correlations with anxiety/dependence and task switching suggest that these attitudes may not directly predict competence, though they could influence technology use indirectly. Recent studies affirm the strong link between digital competence and positive technology attitudes. Abella and Dela Rosa (2023) found that teachers with higher digital literacy reported greater confidence and openness toward technology integration. Similarly, Belisario (2024) highlighted that positive attitudes significantly predict technology utilization, reinforcing the finding that competence and positivity are mutually reinforcing. The negative correlation between

competence and negative attitudes aligns with Limpot (2023), who noted that limited digital skills often foster resistance and reluctance to adopt new technologies. The non-significant results for anxiety and task switching echo findings by the previous study emphasized that competence is more strongly shaped by confidence and training than by multitasking preferences or dependence anxieties (Vuorikari, et al, 2022). The findings affirm that digital competence is closely tied to supervisors' technology attitudes. Positive attitudes enhance competence, while negative attitudes hinder it. This suggests that professional development should not only build technical skills but also foster constructive mindsets toward technology. By addressing both competence and attitudes, instructional supervisors can be better prepared to lead digital transformation in schools.

Conclusions

The study concludes that instructional supervisors in the DepEd Dumaguete City Division generally possess substantial supervisory experience and demonstrate high levels of digital competence, particularly in the areas of safety, information management, and communication. However, limited participation in ICT-related training remains evident, which may explain comparatively lower competence in content creation and problem-solving. Despite these limitations, the respondents exhibited highly positive attitudes toward technology, as reflected in their recognition of its benefits, reliance on digital tools, minimal negative perceptions, and ability to maintain focus while using technology.

The findings further reveal that digital competence and technology attitudes are significantly influenced by selected profile variables, namely position, instructional supervisory experience, and ICT-related training. Although position and supervisory experience were significantly related to digital competence, the negative correlations indicate that occupying higher positions and having longer years of service do not automatically lead to greater digital competence. Higher-ranking supervisors often assume broader administrative and leadership responsibilities, reducing their direct involvement with digital tools and technology-based tasks. Likewise, more experienced supervisors may face greater challenges adapting to rapidly evolving technologies compared with those who entered the profession during the digital age. These findings underscore the importance of continuous professional development and lifelong learning in ensuring that instructional supervisors remain digitally competent regardless of their position or years of experience.

Among the profile variables examined, ICT-related training emerged as the strongest factor associated with digital competence and positive technology attitudes. This highlights the crucial role of professional development in enhancing supervisors' technological knowledge, skills, confidence, and readiness to integrate digital tools into their professional practice. Exposure to ICT-focused learning opportunities also appears to foster more favorable perceptions and greater acceptance of technology.

Moreover, the study confirms a significant relationship between digital competence and technology attitudes. Supervisors with more positive attitudes toward technology tended to demonstrate higher levels of digital competence, whereas those with stronger negative

attitudes exhibited lower competence. These findings suggest that competence and attitudes are mutually reinforcing. Overall, strengthening ICT-related training and cultivating positive technology attitudes are essential for enhancing digital competence and preparing instructional supervisors to effectively lead and sustain digital transformation initiatives in schools.

Recommendations

Based on the significant findings, the following recommendations were postulated:

1. *Strengthen ICT-Related Training Programs.* Educational administrators should design and implement regular, targeted ICT training programs for instructional supervisors, particularly focusing on content creation and problem-solving skills, which were identified as weaker areas of digital competence.
2. *Sustain and Enhance Digital Competence Development.* Schools and the Division Office should provide continuous professional development opportunities to maintain and further improve the already high levels of digital competence, especially in communication, information management, and digital safety.
3. *Promote Technology Integration in Supervisory Functions.* Instructional supervisors should be encouraged to consistently integrate digital tools in supervision practices such as classroom observation, feedback delivery, and instructional monitoring to further strengthen applied digital competence.
4. *Reinforce Positive Technology Attitudes.* Since positive attitudes toward technology are linked with higher digital competence, school leaders should cultivate and sustain favorable perceptions of technology through mentoring, peer-sharing, and recognition of best practices in digital use.
5. *Develop Support Mechanisms for Technological Challenges.* Schools should establish technical support systems or ICT focal persons to assist instructional supervisors in addressing technical issues, thereby improving their confidence in problem-solving and reducing reliance-related difficulties.
6. *Future Research Directions.* Future researchers may conduct similar studies using a larger sample or different educational divisions to validate and expand the findings. Further studies may also explore qualitative approaches to gain deeper insights into how training, leadership roles, and attitudes influence digital competence development among educational leaders.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to established ethical principles throughout the research process. Prior to data collection, formal permission to conduct the study was secured from the city division office. Respondents were fully informed of the study's purpose, objectives, and procedures, and their participation was entirely voluntary.

Informed consent was obtained from all participants before completing the survey questionnaire, with assurances that they could withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained by excluding any personally identifiable information in the reporting of findings. Data were used solely for academic and research purposes and stored securely to protect respondent privacy.

The researcher ensured that the study posed no physical, psychological, or professional harm to participants, and that honesty, integrity, and objectivity guided the collection, analysis, and presentation of results to uphold the credibility and reliability of the findings.

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